

EUthMappers - Learning by Teaching Mapping

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EUthMappers is an ERASMUS+ initiative that promotes STEAM education in secondary schools throughout the European Union, enhancing students' digital skills and fostering environmental civic engagement [1]. The project fa. The idea is to establish an European mapping network similar to YouthMappers. This presentation outlines the project's implementation steps and showcases the remarkable results achieved by participating students.

The study aims to explore the possibility of integrating mapping as a necessary STEAM subject to engage students in exploring their surroundings and applying learning skills to contribute to humanitarian projects remotely. This research goal is then broken down into three smaller components that correspond to three phases of the project: creating accessible educational materials for students, guiding students to map their local environments, and participating in global humanitarian projects.

The project involves three universities (Politecnico di Milano, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, and Presovska Univerzita V Presov) and five secondary schools located in Italy, Spain, Slovakia, Romania, and Portugal, engaging approximately 160 students in total. The management of the project is done by Euronike, which is an association expert in capacity building activities and EU policies. Until now, the project has been running for two years, and was implemented in three phases.

- (1) Development of training materials: a comprehensive training package on open geospatial tools and data analysis was written and made available in six languages (English, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Slovakian and Romanian) [2]. This training was first delivered to teachers, who then transferred the knowledge to their students.
- (2) Local mapping projects: under the guidance of their teachers and with university collaboration, students developed local mapping initiatives from ideation to implementation, focusing on data acquisition and visualization techniques [3]. Across five European cities, students carried out mapping-focused projects that combined local engagement with practical outcomes. In Rovereto (Italy), students identified drainage channels on forest roads in the "Bosco della Città" as a central issue and mapped them using GPS and drone imagery. Since such features had

never been mapped on OSM, they engaged with the OSM community to propose and share a new mapping methodology. The resulting maps and database now support both routine and extraordinary maintenance by the Rovereto Forestry Service, helping mitigate hydrogeological risks. In Madrid (Spain), students mapped key elements related to mobility, leisure spaces, and climate shelters in the Arganzuela neighborhood. Working in groups, they identified and analyzed public space features, and then proposed concrete improvements to enhance young people's quality of life, which they presented at local events and forums. In Prešov (Slovakia), students focused on tree mapping in central city parks. After ecological training, they collected detailed data—such as species, trunk width, and height—using practical tools and mobile apps. Their results contributed to urban ecological databases and were showcased to the public during their school's open-door day. In Lisbon (Portugal), students explored how graffiti and street art reflect local identity by mapping urban artworks around their school. Through documentation and critical analysis, they created a record of artistic interventions with social and historical value, culminating in a community event promoting dialogue on youth expression in public space. In Pitești (Romania), students diagnosed low public awareness of recycling facilities and mapped the location, accessibility, and types of waste accepted at collection points. Their interactive map aimed to make recycling easier and more visible, encouraging environmental responsibility across the city. All the data obtained by students is contributed to the OSM platform. These projects show how students-led mapping activities can generate innovative tools, influence local planning, and foster active citizenship.

- (3) Humanitarian mapping collaboration: as the final activity, students participated in a humanitarian mapping project issued by the United Nations Global Service Centre (UNGSC). There were two workshops about humanitarian mapping and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in order to provide students basic knowledge about humanitarian mapping and their contribution to common goods [4,5]. Students are then trained on humanitarian mapping simulation projects before actually participating in a real-world scenario proposed by UN Maps, a programme in UNGSC to enhance UN peacekeeping missions operational capabilities through open geospatial information. The training project on OSM Sandbox took place in Idlib refugee camps in Syria (Figure 1), while during the actual project students map building data to contribute to generate a three-dimensional digital replica of the city Kandahar, Afghanistan [6]. The generated graphical replica can be used by the UNAMA mission engaging in Virtual Reality (VR) applications to train peacekeeping officers and as a collaborative tool for security and operational briefings. This final phase expanded students' collaborative abilities beyond their classrooms to engage in a meaningful humanitarian project with international impact.

EuthMappers project 27 contributions diagram

Figure 1. Contributions by the students throughout training phases in mapping buildings in Idlib refugee camps, Idlib, Syria.

Throughout these activities, students developed teamwork capabilities, creative thinking skills, and innovative data collection methodologies. Not to mention that, the project's partners also had to think outside the box so as to deliver complicated insights particularly geospatial technology, OSM, collaborative and humanitarian mapping, to the students in the most intuitive way possible. These results would then be demonstrated in two primary aspects, including: (A) statistics and data visualization of student mapping results, and (B) the use of interactive quizzes and creative mapping support tools.

For the first aspect, activities throughout the project were measured and evaluated quantitatively and qualitatively. For the local mapping projects, all changes to OSM were counted and validated based on the topic chosen by the students. The local government presentations are also a way to evaluate the quality of the activities. In two remote workshops, all quiz answers are then statistically analyzed to understand the level of student engagement with each topic. The humanitarian mapping process then extracts, analyzes, and visualizes data from OSM to monitor each student's process.

In the second aspect, interactive workshop tools were developed to increase online engagement and address limited physical interaction. Python-based quizzes that progressed from simple questions to discussion forums and a world map opinion sharing feature were built on the Streamlit platform for easy modification and reuse. Custom OpenStreetMap (OSM) editors were developed to increase digital accessibility, allowing students to practice mapping on OSM Sandbox servers. The iSandbox4ALL application, with a smartphone-friendly interface, followed by the iD4All application for live OSM mapping, allows students to map on smartphones as well. Finally, Python notebooks were created for data collection, statistics, and 3D map visualization, providing detailed weekly reports of student contributions (python notebook and 3D web map of the training can be found in [7]).

In conclusion the EuthMappers project is a mapping playground not only for students but also for educators. Through dynamic mapping activities, students collaborate to identify local and global challenges and address them using geospatial technology. Humanitarian mapping encourages students to develop empathy and participate meaningfully in global emergency initiatives. By involving high school students, the project has achieved cross-institutional partnerships, advanced STEAM teaching methods and technologies, and created a flexible framework for local community mapping with people from a variety of backgrounds and approaches.

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